

A Variable Stiffness Approach to Vibration Control

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Abstract : This work introduces a new concept for controlling the mechanical vibrations via variable stiffness coil spring. The concept relies on fitting a screw through the spring to change the number of active spring coils. A prototype has been built and tested with promising results toward an innovation in the field of vibration control.

Keywords : variable stiffness, coil spring, vibration control, computer science

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